

Contract No: 690474

EKLIPSE

Establishing a European Knowledge and Learning Mechanism to Improve the Policy-Science-Society Interface on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services

Call: H2020-SC5-2014-2015

Topic: SC5-10c2015

Deliverable 5.2 (D5.2)

Report outlining reasons for willingness of networks to engage in the mechanism and identification of potential incentives and capacity building needs

WP5: Engaging with networks and other relevant stakeholders

Due date of deliverable: 31/01/2018

Actual submission date: 31/01/2018

Start date of project: 01/02/2016 **Duration:** 48 months

Name of Participant responsible for this deliverable: UPORTO

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Revision: Second Version (V2.0)

Dissemination level: Public

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1 Executive Summary

The aim of this deliverable is to further improve the 'network of networks' model of EKLIPSE and to engage new actors within it. The three key questions, answered in the report, included the following ones: 1) how existing networks function; 2) what kind of knowledge and capacity gaps exist and which conditions are required to foster more effective interactions at the science-policy interface, and 3) what kind of expectations do existing networks have towards EKLIPSE.

Qualitative and quantitative data were collected and critically analysed in two iterative rounds to shed light on key aspects of networking and to improve the EKLIPSE Network of Networks (NoN). In the first, pilot phase of the data collection process, between September 2016 and January 2017, one interview was conducted and 5 long questionnaires were collected and analysed. Based on the findings and methodological experiences gained, both questionnaire and interview questions were modified. In the second phase of data collection, between May 2017 and January 2018, 128 respondents answered to a short questionnaire through the UNIPARK online survey platform, and 21 interviews were carried out. Questionnaires were filled by regular network members, while for the interviews we contacted lead representatives of selected networks (e.g. president, board member, communication and networking officer or secretary). Although diverse audience was targeted, scientists and networks with a strong research orientation are overrepresented among the respondents.

Existing networks included in the research showed diverse characteristics. The networks have quite similar and standard/conventional governing and decision-making structures, but (informally) some members are always more active while others are rather passive. Except some of the learned societies, existing networks engage a wide range of actors, from scientists and practitioners to NGOs and policy-makers. Decision making structures and procedures are generally heterogeneous. Smaller and more focused networks tend to have a simpler governance model (either governed by its members or by a small central body), while large networks including a diverse range of actors have more formalized decision making structures, and several governance bodies (e.g. executive board, advisors, and secretariat). Funding is a key constraint for many of the networks interviewed, therefore diversifying the revenue sources is an important strategy for many of them.

Science-policy-society interfaces are familiar phenomena to networks and their membership who answered our questions, most of them already taking part in such interactions. The general perception suggests that the more diverse actors involved, the more effective the science-policy-interface. Key actors to be included are scientists with background in multiple disciplines, policy-makers from the national to the EU level or even broader, and representatives of the civil society and the business sector. Engaging citizens in science-policy-society interfaces is a contested topic. Our respondents mostly suggested to engage citizens indirectly, through representative organizations (NGOs). However, organizations or networks that focus on citizen engagement were underrepresented in our sample, therefore the above finding might be a result of ignorance or perceived irrelevance in science-dominated networks. Networks and their membership face several challenges at the science-policy-society interface, ranging from limited resources (funding, staff and time available) and tensions within and between existing networks to effectively communicate and create relevant impact. Challenges related to the scientific quality of the work, as well as the transparency of and the ethical infrastructures behind the interfaces were perceived less important.

Several capacity and knowledge gaps were revealed by the study, which hinder effective participation in science-policy-society interactions and could be improved by targeted capacity building actions. These included knowledge gaps with thematic foci (e.g. uncertainty, ES disservices, assessment) and

concerning the way how science can link up with the policy cycle; capacity gaps in communication, networking and knowledge generation/sharing, and capacity gaps in networks' administrative functioning (e.g. fund raising, human resources etc.). Preferred tools for capacity building included trainings, workshop and conferences, and some less conventional formats engaging a truly diverse audience (e.g. matchmaking, hackathon). The perception of the usefulness of online tools, such as webinars, was different in the questionnaires and the interviews. While network representatives suggested webinars as a well-functioning tool to engage a broad audience, going beyond the national scale and the regular membership of a given network, survey respondents rarely listed webinars among the effective tools for capacity building, indicating that those who replied to our questionnaire do not participate webinars regularly, or do not find them useful.

Expectations towards EKLIPSE were manifold. The mechanism is expected to identify and engage relevant stakeholders in the dialogue between science, policy and society. It is suggested to have a role in knowledge generation and synthesis through engaging and motivating experts and creating a knowledge base. It is supposed to effectively disseminate results, which means that key messages should be delivered to target audiences in a clear but robust format. EKLIPSE is also expected to join forces with existing networks and help them to establish or strengthen relationships within and between networks, as well as between networks and other actors of the science-policy-society interface. Here a key issue is to avoid duplications with existing initiatives. Finally, EKLIPSE is considered to have a role in improving science-policy-society interactions in general by creating a formal, long-lasting but flexible *“process through which policy problems can be transformed into scientific problems and vice versa”* (quote from an interviewee).

Potential contributions to EKLIPSE showed variability, depending on existing capacities and willingness to undertake different roles in the science-policy-society interface. In general, survey respondents and interviewees felt more comfortable to offer contributions related to thematic or/and methodological expertise or acting as a knowledge hub, rather than provide management support or act as evaluators of the process. It is up to EKLIPSE and the future mechanism to identify the appropriate manner and incentives to create long-lasting and fruitful collaborations.

The EKLIPSE Network of Networks (NoN) was considered to have a potentially important role in organising science-policy-society interactions in the field of biodiversity and ecosystem services. Nevertheless, communicating the principles, structures and processes of EKLIPSE would be useful to make clear the 'differentia specifica' and added values of the mechanism, as well as its formal links to existing initiatives. The well-established and larger the network (or if it is already a type of NoN), the harder to show them the added values of the EKLIPSE NoN. Smaller and more focused networks are more interested in a NoN, but might struggle with lack of resources to get engaged. Based on the analysis of the interviewed network's external relationships, multiple networks have been identified which can act as liaison-points or ambassadors for science-policy-society interface regarding biodiversity and ecosystem services. EKLIPSE should focus on expanding collaborations with networks which can provide access to disciplines beyond the environmental one (economic, social), as well as to organisations which can expand collaboration with society (NGOs).

General recommendations from research participants highlighted that 1) duplications with existing initiatives should be avoided, clear roles and collaborations should be established. 2) Knowledge exchange and co-creation should be supported across different levels and knowledge forms. Incentivizing knowledge-holders is of key importance to this end. 3) A wide variety of actors – e.g. business and society – should be engaged, although the exact way and content of these interactions are yet to be settled. 4) Attention should be paid to have a balanced regional representation across Europe e.g. via a network of country representatives, or by having targeted support for CEE countries.

2 Introduction

Many initiatives exist in Europe and beyond to improve the use of scientific and other knowledge forms in policy decisions related to biodiversity and ecosystem services (see the IPBES as the major global platform for science-policy interactions). Nevertheless, many of such initiatives are facing challenges in terms of effective communication, mobilization of diverse knowledge forms, and implementation of research findings, mainly because science-policy interactions are understood as linear processes (Young et al. 2014). The SPIRAL and the KNEU projects engaged various actors of the science-policy interface in a participatory dialogue and provided recommendations at the European scale to improve science-policy interactions. Three basic functions were identified that should be fulfilled in order to make the science-policy interface more effective, which include (1) the synthesis of available knowledge, (2) the development of a common research strategy, as well as (3) networking and capacity building (Nesshöver et al. 2016).

Different institutional setups can be designed to implement the above functions, but two main types stand out: the network approach and the platform approach (Görg et al. 2016). On the one hand, the network approach suggests an open and light model, complementary to existing structures, which engages individual network members on a voluntary (self-registered) basis. The platform approach, on the other hand, suggests a membership at the organizational level, which needs a stronger governance structure, and while guarantees rights to member organizations, also imposes requirements on them (Görg et al. 2016). As the transition between these two extreme ends is gradual, the KNEU project developed a hybrid approach as well, mixing features of the network based and the platform approach (KNEU Team, 2014), which also served as the main building block for developing the governance structure of EKLIPSE. The mechanism being developed by EKLIPSE seeks to identify evidence relevant to decision-making by establishing dialogue between science, policy and society. To this end, the major supporting objective of EKLIPSE, especially of WP5, is to promote the engagement of those networks, including structured scientific network, informal ones, communities of practice, learned societies, etc., whose knowledge has a key potential impact on biodiversity, ecosystem services and related environmental challenges in a 'network of networks' (Watt et al., forthcoming).

This deliverable (D5.2) provides a critical analysis of the 'network of networks' model of EKLIPSE from the point of view of existing networks and their membership by:

- a) understanding how existing networks function and deriving the key lessons for developing EKLIPSE's own network,
- b) identifying gaps in knowledge and capacity and exploring contextual conditions that are required to foster more effective interactions at the science-policy interface, and
- c) exploring the expectations of existing networks towards EKLIPSE and the possible forms / aspects of collaboration.

Additionally, the deliverable aims at further improving the 'network of networks' model and engaging new actors in EKLIPSE. We wanted to analyse both the advantages and incentives, as well as possible drawbacks and hindering factors of the NoN from the perspectives of existing networks and from these findings develop the EKLIPSE NoN's added value. To reach this general objective we carried out empirical research with network representatives (based on an online questionnaire and semi-structured interviews) and critically analysed the key aspects of networking in the field of biodiversity

and ecosystem services. In the next section (Chapter 3), we introduce the data and the methods we applied, and discuss some of the limitations of the approach used. Additionally, the questionnaire, the interview guideline and the list of contacted networks are presented in the Annex. In the Results section (Chapter 4), the questionnaire and interview results are analysed in detail, and also a brief comparison is provided to identify patterns of convergence and divergence between the two data sources. Key findings are discussed in Chapter 5, with special emphasis on recommendations for the further development of the EKLIPSE mechanism and the network of networks.

3 Research methodology

3.1 General research strategy

We applied a mixed (qualitative and quantitative) and iterative research strategy (see fig. 1) in order to triangulate data and increase the reliability of the results. In the first, pilot phase, we developed a long and detailed online questionnaire form, including both open-ended and single/multiple choice questions, and invited network participants to fill the questionnaire online, using the UNIPARK platform (<https://www.unipark.com/en/>), between September and December 2016. Additionally, this long questionnaire was used to prepare a face-to-face interview in January 2017, to check the ability of the questions to provide in-depth and comprehensive data on the key aspects of networking. Draft results in the first phase indicated that the questionnaire was too long and complicated, and therefore not appealing enough for network participants to devote the time required. During the 4-month long pilot period, only 5 respondents answered the questions in detail via the online form, 4 of them invited in person. This experience was reinforced by the face-to-face interview, which lasted for 3 hours, and while it provided good occasion for a critical and in-depth conversation between the interviewee and the interviewer about EKLIPSE, it was too demanding in terms of time.

Based on the experience gained in the first phase, we divided the long questionnaire into two separate parts. Most closed-ended questions from the original questionnaire were put together and re-arranged into a short questionnaire, which needed 15-20 minutes to fill. In addition, open-ended questions and a few closed-ended ones from the original questionnaire were used to create a semi-structured interview guide, tested to last approximately for 1 hour to answer. In order not to lose data collected earlier, and because questions highly overlapped, online and face-to-face responses to the original long questionnaire was analysed together with the semi-structured interviews.

Figure 1. Research timeline

Data collection and analysis, as well as sample characteristics concerning the questionnaire and the semi-structured interviews are discussed in more detail in the next two sections, respectively. The

original long questionnaire, the short questionnaire and the semi-structured interview guideline are presented in the Annex.

3.2 Online questionnaire

The basic idea behind the online questionnaire design was to create a questionnaire which is easy and quick to answer, but which enables researchers to collect key information on the expectations, needs and most favoured communication channels of network members. Finally we ended up with a questionnaire of 9 content-specific questions and a short question block for background data, such as the name of the network represented and name and e-mail address of the respondent and if she/he wanted to become part of the EKLIPSE community. Out of these questions, only 3 were marked as obligatory (including potential contributions to EKLIPSE (Q4), favoured communication channels (Q8) and the name of the network represented). Name and e-mail address of the respondents (in case they shared it with us) were filtered and stored separately from the database in order to guarantee anonymity during the analysis. The questions were analysed with the SPSS software, using descriptive statistics (frequencies, cross tabulations and compare means). The open-ended questions were analysed by thematic content analysis. The significance level in case of the compare means and cross-tabulations is $p=0.05$.

Questionnaires were available online (no paper version provided) via the UNIPARK platform (at <https://www.unipark.com/en/>), accessible from various browsers without authentication (i.e. invitation or password). Cookies were used to avoid duplicating responses by one respondents, but IP addresses were not stored. Conferences, trainings and workshops were used as typical occasions to advertise the questionnaire and invite people to take part (e.g. Alter-NET 2017 conference¹, ESEE 2017 conference and summer school², SCB Europe section 2017 summer school³, etc.). In addition, the questionnaire was announced at the general EKLIPSE communication channels (eg. website, forum, ResearchGate, and generalized e-mail through the EKLIPSE keep-me-posted database), and invitations were sent out through personalized e-mails to relevant networks.

According to the DoW, a minimum of 100 questionnaires had to be collected from various types of respondents, such as members of steering committees, communication officers, data managers and regular members from the full range of networks at the regional and European scales whose knowledge and/or activities have a key impact on biodiversity and ecosystem services. Between May and December 2017 the online questionnaire was accessed altogether 432 times, 128 respondents started to answer the questionnaire (response rate=29.63%), and 62 respondents went through all the questions (completion rate=14.35%). The mean processing time was 13 min 26 sec. Drop-outs were most frequent after Q1 about whom to involve at the science-policy-society interface ($n=16$), Q4 about the potential contribution to EKLIPSE ($n=11$), Q2 about challenges at the science-policy-society interface ($n=8$), and at the last question about the contact details ($n=7$). We suppose that drop-outs in the first two questions might have appeared because respondents realized that they have no interest or experience in the topic, while drop-outs at Q4 might indicate that respondents felt uncomfortable to answer a question about potential contributions because they did not want to commit themselves to EKLIPSE.

Respondents represented altogether 36 different networks (table 1). Mostly one response was collected per network, although there were 6 networks where more than one member filled the

¹ <http://www.alter-net.info/outputs/conf-2017>

² <http://esee2017budapest.org/>

³ <http://sccc.okologia.mta.hu/node/228>

questionnaire. Some of the respondents found it difficult to commit themselves to one network – some respondents therefore indicated that they were independent representing themselves in the questionnaire (n=5), being part of several networks (n=3), or identified their network with their professional field (e.g. network of ecologists) (n=5). Most of the respondents identified themselves as scientists, although some respondents (n=6) indicated to have several professional backgrounds (fig. 2). As no other professional data of the respondents were recorded, we have no information on which level of the membership is represented.

Table 1. Networks represented in the survey

Networks represented by more than 1 respondent	Network-Forum for Biodiversity Research Germany (n=4), IPBES (n=3), ALTER-Net (n=2), IUCN (n=2), UK Urban Ecology Forum (n=2), University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences Vienna (n=2)
Networks represented by 1 respondent	BDEM (Bureau des Etudiants et Doctorants du Muséum), BiodivERsA, Centre for Forestry Research and Development, CNR ISAC, EMR impacts, ESA Environment&Society Research Network, EU BON, EU MAES assessment, GEM-CON-BIO, Hungarian Academy of Sciences, IFLA, INSPIRES project, Institut Pasteur de Tunis, Institut Pasteur International Network, Italian Ecosystem Services Alliance, Italian National Research Council, James Hutton Institute, Leverage Points for Sustainability Transformation, LTER, Platform for Research of Landscape and Ecosystem Services, Porto University, Public Health Services, Qessa project, OPERAs project, Silva Mediterranean Working Group on Urban and Peri-urban forests, ULB, University Fernando Pessoa, University of Szeged, University of the Aegean

Figure 2. Type of actors answering the questionnaire

In spite of the pilot phase and the following restructuring of the research strategy, we still faced some challenges during data collection and analysis. A major challenge was to *attract people* to fill the questionnaire, which can be an indication of not using efficiently enough the existing communication channels, or not articulating clear enough the aims/expected outcomes of the questionnaire so that people who accessed the questionnaire did not find it relevant. Based on feedback received from some of the respondents we also realized that EKLIPSE’s broad understanding of ‘networks’ and question no. 4 concerning potential contributions to EKLIPSE activities might have been *difficult to understand* for people who were not yet familiar with the mechanism. Even though we provided links to additional information (youtube video about the working procedure to handle requests and written material on the EKLIPSE website), processing this additional information might have required more time than expected from respondents.

3.3 Semi-structured interview

Semi-structured interviews were designed to allow reflection on how existing networks function and what kind of challenges they face (incl. 8 questions from Q1 to Q8), to share expectations towards EKLIPSE and potential rooms for collaboration (incl. 5 question from Q9 to Q12 plus Q14), and to map the level of interaction between existing networks (one question, Q14). The first set of questions provided us with best practices and key lessons learnt which can be utilized to further improve the EKLIPSE mechanism and its future business model. The second set of questions directly focused on the networking activities of EKLIPSE, i.e. how EKLIPSE could support existing networks and vice versa. Question no. 14 aimed at collecting data on how networks interact with each other to update the EKLIPSE network of networks concept and dynamic map (EKLIPSE Deliverable 5.1.). While most questions were open-ended qualitative questions, two of the questions were single-choice (concerning the potential contributions to EKLIPSE and the interactions with existing networks), and another four questions combined the open-ended question with a structured, multiple-choice question. Qualitative and quantitative questions were mixed for two reasons: to allow comparison of the questionnaire and the interview results (concerning potential contributions to EKLIPSE), and to complete qualitative analysis with quantitative data for some well-structured aspects of networking.

Existing networks, operating at European or regional level, were selected for the interview from a database prepared on the basis of previous projects (i.e. KNEU) and research work (EKLIPSE Deliverable D5.1). The key principles of the selection process was 1) to contact those networks which are the most relevant and active in terms of science-policy interfacing for biodiversity and ecosystem services; and 2) to contact diverse networks in terms of involved actors (i.e. science, policy and practice including the NGO and the business sector) and scientific fields (from more natural scientific to more social scientific as well as interdisciplinary networks) (see the Annex for the list of contacted networks). Altogether 22 interviews were conducted, and an additional 5 long questionnaires (covering all the interview questions and filled electronically in the first phase) were included in the analysis (total n=27).

According to the DoW, a total number of 25 semi-structured interviews was envisaged to carry out with members of steering committees (20% of respondents), communication officers (20% of respondents), data managers (20% of respondents), and regular members (40% of respondents) from the full range of networks in society (20% of respondents), science (20% of respondents), business (20% of respondents) and policy (20% of respondents). In terms of the networks operating at the regional scale, we aimed to have a representative sample with one third of questionnaires and interviews in Northern Europe, one third in Southern Europe and one third in Central and Eastern Europe.

To what extent the above-mentioned target of members was achieved turned out rather challenging to evaluate. The question was not explicitly asked during the interviews and would probably have been difficult for the respondents to answer as well since interviewees might hold different or several roles simultaneously. Also some of the especially larger networks might work both in society and science or other combinations. The regional scale was later neglected as a condition for the networks interviewed because many of the networks had broader range than Southern, Northern or Eastern Europe. Since the term network was understood very broadly as including different kinds of “organized exchange” – e.g. informal thematic networks, formal networks of institutions, learned societies, NGOs, projects, etc. it is difficult to categorize the networks. However, some coarse distinctions can be made of the 27 networks interviewed:

Table 2. Networks interviewed (full names are shown in the Annex)

Projects:	AtlantOS, ECOPOTENTIAL, ESMERALDA, GENIALG, HERCULES, Leverage Points, MERCES,	7
NGOs:	CEEWeb, Earthwatch, EEB, IUCN	4
Expert/ practitioner organizations:	EFB, Eurosite, ICES, Greifswald Mire Centre	4
Learned societies:	ESA EN, ESEE, ESRS, SCB	4
Science-policy interfaces:	ALTER-Net, BioDivERSA, EPBRS, EUROMarine, GEOBON, NeFo, OPPLA, Platform for Research of Landscape and Ecosystem Services	7

Section 4.2 will describe some major characteristics and attributes of the networks and aims to make distinctions between them.

On behalf of the networks, lead representatives (i.e. the president, board members, communication or networking officer) were contacted to make the interviews. 8 interviews were made face-to-face, while the rest was done via skype. Interview questions were a priori shared with the interviewees. Written notes were prepared for all the interviews,⁴ which was sent back to the interviewees for checking any errors or misunderstandings. Then all data was uploaded to the UNIPARK server to store them securely and anonymously. The length of the interviews varied between 30 minutes and 3 hours, being 60-70 minutes the average. Interview notes were analysed with qualitative and thematic content analysis.

The interview situation allowed us to provide more detailed description of the key concepts of activities of EKLIPSE to the respondents, therefore results might be more reliable than in the case of the questionnaires. The dialogue based format also helped the respondents to share their reflections about the 'network of networks model'. Nevertheless, asking representatives to answer questions on behalf of their network also created challenges, especially at Q9 (Potential contributions to EKLIPSE) and Q13 (Interactions with other networks), because some networks which are loosely defined collaborate with others through their members (i.e. the representative could not commit the network only its membership, and could not talk about the interactions of her network with others, only about interactions between the membership and other networks).

Altogether 32 networks were contacted for interviews, and 22 individual interviews were made (in addition to the 5 long questionnaires filled by respondents in the first phase). Personal contacts, first and second hand, and previous working relationship seemed to increase the willingness of the contacted organizations/people to take part in the interview, even though a quarter of the interviewees came from outside of the project consortia contacts. The fact that both interviewees and survey respondents came from the closer circles around EKLIPSE indicates that engaging a wider range of potentially interested actors is quite difficult, as the relevance and added value of the mechanism might not be so evident to them. This might especially apply for organizations having a strong citizen engagement element. Although several attempts were made to invite them in the study, this type of networks remained underrepresented, which makes it difficult to judge whether and how citizens (or their representative bodies) should be engaged in the mechanism. This is however a crucial issue, on the one hand because EKLIPSE would like to set up a science-policy-**society** interface and, on the other hand, because the questionnaires also showed contested results in terms of citizens being included in the mechanism directly, or via representing organizations, or not at all.

⁴ Recordings were made only for four interviews, in these cases we asked for the consent of the interviewee in advance.

4 Questionnaire results

4.1 Experience on the science-policy interface

Responses to Question 1 indicate that effective science-policy-society interactions should include multiple actors, such as scientists with different disciplinary background, policy-makers at different levels, and representatives of the civil society (table 3). Decision-makers at the national level, and natural and social scientists proved to be the most important actors to be involved, followed by decision-makers at the EU level and by representatives of the civil society. Citizens and other scientists are generally considered less important participants of the science-policy interface (SPI). Looking at the standard deviations we can see that consensus around the involvement of national level decision-makers and social scientist is the highest.

Table 3. Actors to be involved in science-policy-society interactions

Actors to be involved	Mean	Std. Deviation	Modus	Share of very important (5) (%)
Natural scientists	4.67	0.777	5	80.0
Social scientists	4.61	0.567	5	65.3
Other scientists	3.97	0.930	4	32.0
Representatives for civil society	4.32	0.829	5	51.3
Citizens	4.05	1.077	5	46.7
Decision-makers at European scale	4.48	0.747	5	60.4
Decision-makers at national scale	4.70	0.545	5	72.6
Representatives of specific networks	4.23-4.45		5	58.0

Cross-tabulation analysis shows no significant differences of the above results along the different backgrounds of the respondents (science, policy or society, the latter one referring to representing the civil society through NGOs), partly due to the small number of respondents with non-scientific backgrounds. However, it is remarkable that citizens were considered more important to be involved by respondents with a mixed background or with a background in the NGO sector (average values range between 4.33 and 5) than by policy-makers and researchers (average values range between 3 and 3.93), which indicates that the willingness of citizens representatives to participate at the SPI might be higher than the actual room provided for them.

Respondents also listed several other networks that should be involved in science-policy-society interactions. Farmers/land-users (including agriculture, fisheries and forestry) and business actors (industry players and supply chain actors) were mentioned most frequently (10 and 9 times, respectively), followed by NGOs (especially those working with conservation), regional and local decision-makers, and other local stakeholders (6 times, each). Responses also indicate that science-policy-society interactions are considered by some as multilevel processes, suggesting that actors from the local to the global level (i.e. UN and its institutions) might be relevant to invite. Sectors that have a less direct relation with biodiversity and ecosystem services management – namely the public health sector, water management and tourism – were mentioned rarely. Some respondents used this question as an opportunity to name existing networks which they think important to engage, such as the ALTER-Net, associations of landscape planners (e.g. IFLA/IALE), the Ecosystem Service Partnership (ESP), and relevant national scientific networks (e.g. the Finnish Society for Environmental Social Science, YHYS).

At question 2, respondents indicated that acting at the science-policy-society interface is quite challenging, especially in terms of time devoted and the strength of relationships between the different actors (figure 3). Cross-tabulation analysis to check the relationship between the background of the respondents and the type of challenges faces did not show significant patterns.

Figure 3. Challenges faced at the science-policy-society interface

Respondents added quite a few other challenges to the a priori list. These were mostly related to **communication** (e.g. “Clarity of communication across scientific disciplines” or the need for a “Common language between actors”), to the **legitimacy of the processes** organized at the science-policy-society interface (e.g. “Mandate and acceptance of process and results by actors, esp. from policy” or “Equal opportunity for expert to get involved” or “Neutral facilitation”) and to the **acknowledgement** of the work done by contributing knowledge-holders (e.g. “Funding and acknowledgement system: At the moment researchers get paid by # scientific publications and not for their S-P-S interface contributions”). Several other challenges, mentioned in the open text box, relate to the ones listed a priori, which further reinforces their relevance. Although listed only once, challenges in science education and the difficulty to generalize results/solutions from the local or regional scale are important ones, which highlights that the dialogue between science, policy and society is inherently characterized by structural difficulties and complexity.

4.2 EKLIPSE as a science-policy-society interface

Respondents considered EKLIPSE as a relatively important mechanism to strengthen links between the different actors of the science-policy-society interface (table 4). Most respondents indicated that EKLIPSE could best improve the relationship between policy-makers and scientists, between scientists and networks, and between policy-makers and networks, but the potential of EKLIPSE to improve relationships between civil society and networks, scientists or policy-makers was perceived only as moderate. This indicates that for most respondents EKLIPSE acts primarily at the science-policy interface, and expectations are lower in terms of civil society engagement. This result might be influenced by the underrepresentation of respondents having background in the NGO sector.

Table 4. The role of EKLIPSE in strengthening interactions between the actors of the SPI

The role of EKLIPSE in strengthening the interaction...	Mean	Std. Deviation	Modus	Share of very essential (5) (%)
... between policy-makers and scientist	4.03	0.928	4	36.4
... between policy-makers and networks	3.92	0.777	4	21.5
... between policy-makers and civil society	3.63	1.084	3	27.7
... between networks and scientists	3.94	0.950	4	32.3
... between networks and civil society	3.54	1.076	4	18.5
... between civil society and scientists	3.69	1.145	4	27.7
The science-policy-society interface in general	4.09	0.805	4	33.8

In Question 5, we asked respondents to describe their expectations towards EKLIPSE more specifically (most frequently used words are displayed in Figure 4). The 34 written answers were grouped into 4 major groups. Most responses (n=12) highlighted that EKLIPSE should boost up **networking** along the interface either by helping existing networks and individual actors to establish or strengthen relationships (i.e. through capacity building, supporting science education); or by applying innovative approaches and creating new networks; or by linking up with other well-established knowledge platforms such as IPBES or IUCN. The second group of answers (n=5) emphasised EKLIPSE’s role in **knowledge** generation (i.e. applying citizen science, collect experiential data, access to best available knowledge) and sharing (e.g. via conferences or trainings). Respondents (n=5) also underlined the **policy support** role of EKLIPSE (e.g. EKLIPSE is expected to become an “*easily accessible support mechanism for policy- and decision-makers to base their judgement on different types of knowledge and science*”). The fourth group (n=4) of answers focused on the **working procedures** of EKLIPSE, and highlighted that future viability depends on several factors, such being responsive to policy windows, applying progressive approaches, developing a durable and long-lasting structure, and integrating (instead of competing) with similar other interfaces. The rest of the answers shared either some concerns (e.g. unclear benefits and lack of time from the scientist side, or long-term financial sustainability of the business model), or general visions about EKLIPSE (e.g. “*Ideally EKLIPSE could be a prototype of institutionalized mechanism for trans-disciplinary post-normal problem solving*”).

Figure 4. Keywords related to the expectations towards EKLIPSE

We also asked respondents about which roles they would have been interested to take in the EKLIPSE project and future science-policy mechanism (question 4). We listed 12 different types of potential contributions based on actual functionalities of the mechanism, and asked respondents to rate their interest from 1 to 3, where 1 referred to having no interest in certain roles, 2 referred to having potential interest but lacking knowledge and/or capacity to contribute, and 3 referred to actual interest and capability to fulfilling certain roles. The listed roles were not explained in detail at the question, which might cause some misunderstanding even if the questionnaire provided links to relevant explanations on the EKLIPSE website. Results (fig. 5) shows that respondents were most opened to offer their contribution to provisioning of thematic expertise, followed by provisioning of methodological expertise, knowledge hub role and the evaluation of the work of the mechanism. Provision of tools and infrastructure and management support were the least attractive roles in terms of actual interest, and management support proved to be the last one in terms of possible interest. Very few other roles were mentioned in addition to our list, these included data collection, networking with IPBES, developing new tools and maintaining interconnections among the actors.

Figure 5. Respondents' interest in different EKLIPSE roles

4.3 Capacity building and communication

Questions 6 and 7 focused on capacity gaps and the most efficient ways to fill them. The open question about existing gaps in capacity and knowledge respondents would have liked to fill resulted in 28 answers, some of them listing several gaps to fill, mostly by scientists. Answers were grouped into 5 groups. The largest group (n=14) included **knowledge gaps with thematic foci** (e.g. ecosystem disservices, emission of allergens, effectiveness of voluntary area-based conservation, sustainable food production, or designing healthy green infrastructure). The second group (n=13) focused on gaps in the understanding of how **policy processes** work (e.g. "knowledge of scientists on how interface actually

work”) and in the capacities to actively influence such processes. Direct access (personal contact) to policy-makers and effective ways of communicating scientific results were mentioned by several respondents here. The third group of responses (n=13) highlighted capacity gaps in **knowledge generation and dissemination**. Several respondents mentioned gaps between different knowledge forms (especially the difficulties to access scientific knowledge by citizens, and vice versa), which were linked to overly complex and unclear terminology used by scientists. Designing useful outreach materials, using a common language and applying popular social media channels were mentioned additionally as potential ways of improvement. The fourth group of answers (n=6) focused on **networking**, and listed several skills that are necessary (and actually lacking) for effective networking, e.g. interactivity, facilitation skills, or the ability to work in a diverse team. The last bunch of responses pointed at gaps in **individual capacities**, especially time and financial resources (funding) that might significantly influence a person’s ability to take part in SPI processes.

To overcome capacity and knowledge gaps respondents suggested mainly interactive formats, such as trainings, workshops, matchmaking events and pilot demonstrations (n=15). Conferences were also considered as effective ways of capacity building by quite many respondents (n=10), although this result might reflect a more mainstream scientific approach. Web-based tools such as webinars or online knowledge platforms were listed only 3 times, which indicates that respondents still prefer face-to-face events. Beyond these regular capacity building tools, one more innovative approach was also mentioned by 3 respondents, namely providing funds for joint teams of scientists and policy-makers (and the general public) that can work in an action-oriented way.

Question 9 asked the respondents to choose from a predefined list of communication tools those ones which they use to stay informed and get in touch with different actors engaged in the science-policy-society interface, and then asked them to rank these tools according to their effectiveness. Respondents use various communication channels in parallel (figure 6), among which personalized e-mails seem to be the far most effective (figure 7). Additional communication tools were listed by a few respondents, focusing mainly on scientific dissemination channels (i.e. conferences, papers), websites, or on personal face-to-face contacts. One respondent also mentioned professional company services as a further possibility to increase the effectiveness of communication.

Figure 6. Communication tools used by respondents at the science-policy-society interface

Figure 7. The effectiveness of different communication tools

4.4 General recommendations to EKLIPSE

In the last question of the questionnaire we asked respondents if there were any other issues we should have paid attention to. We received 16 answers, and except for one all of them are from scientists. Table 5 groups these key messages into four main categories.

Table 5. Respondents' general recommendations to EKLIPSE

Engage diverse actors	Strengthen and broaden existing networks
<p>"Be assertive, be clear, be productive (publications), involve citizens!"</p> <p>"It is important to pay attention on the representativeness of the network members in every aspects worked in the context of EKLIPSE."</p> <p>"Somehow make the networks more inclusive to the process, eg. by taking the EKLIPSE stand to their venues and discussing with the management (chair) on personal level; this requires identifying the key networks, others could be networked on a more general level."</p> <p>"The society part should include a strong proportion of indigenous people and local communities and their engagement (maybe it already includes these actors/communities and I am just unaware)."</p> <p>"Think more global and create links with other initiatives in other region (Asia, Africa, etc...)"</p>	<p>"As a UK scientist, I am concerned about maintaining strong networks to science, policy and practice in Europe in the future. I am also concerned about the erosion of standards and the impact that this could have on cross boundary issues."</p> <p>"As scientist I have limited possibilities to interact with policy-makers. Moreover, in my country this interaction is for the 'happy few' often only promoting their own personal interest and not representing others."</p> <p>"Finding way to support national networks where needed (mainly Eastern and Southern Europe) - like was done many years ago via EU projects related to EPBRS"</p> <p>"To find national representative to obtain all links with other networks."</p>

<p>Incentivize/inform scientists</p> <p>“Acknowledge the work of scientists, make it visible.”</p> <p>“Provide more incentives for scientists to participate, e.g. links to research funding opportunities and/or joint work on manuscripts for peer-reviewed journals”</p> <p>“Just by looking at this page now and the survey, it is not obvious how EKLIPSE already forms as network of networks and is more than a H2020 project.”</p>	<p>Support knowledge exchange at various levels</p> <p>“Include a significant role for knowledge brokers - those who are skilled to translate scientific knowledge products into for policy and/or society understandable findings.”</p> <p>“To bring information and interest as much as possible to the local decision-makers/policy actors and citizens.”</p> <p>“Work on a project basis”</p>
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5 Interview results

Results are presented in the order of the interview guide. Section 5.1 will present the general characteristics related to the objectives, functions, governance, funding, and strengths and challenges of the networks. Section 5.2 sheds light on networks' perceptions and expectations towards EKLIPSE, as well as their preferred ways of capacity building and communication. Section 5.3 will analyse networks' potential contribution to EKLIPSE, while Section 5.4 discovers how networks are, if at all, collaborating with other networks. It should be noted that in the multiple choice questions networks could generally choose more than one response, thus the total is not always 27.

5.1 Major characteristics of existing networks

The first question gave the interviewees the opportunity to talk from their perspective about the main objectives and functions of their network; this means that some of networks might have additional functions or objectives that were not mentioned by the interviewee during the interview. Some of the answers were also complemented by information found on the network's website. The answers varied from explanations about more strategic or fundamental objectives and visions such as working for environmental justice or empowering people to the more concrete and visible functions and actions such as conferences, knowledge production and matchmaking that the networks carry out more or less regularly. Initially we tried to make a distinction between theory-oriented or practice-oriented networks, but this was not successful since many of the networks do both types of work. Two of the networks also mentioned that they are, to some extent, networks of networks since they include organisations that are networks in themselves.

Thematic focus of the networks

All of the networks interviewed were chosen because they worked on biodiversity, ecosystem services or some environment-related topics either on national-regional, or the European scale, some even globally. Some of the networks have more focused objectives and worked around rather specific topics (e.g. green roofs, seaweed biomass or cultural landscapes). Networks working on focused topics were often (EU-) projects, which naturally form around a specified topic due to the funder's expectations and the time-limitations of the project or network. However, there were also non-EU-projects that had a specific focus. Broader overarching topics or fields such as environmental conservation (species, biodiversity, marine conservation, etc.) were generally mentioned by long-standing larger networks. The work in multiple and diverse fields happened both in practice and as producing research or knowledge about the field. The larger networks also often had special committees or working groups that would focus then on the more specific topics related to the overarching broader topic.

Functions and activities

Almost all of the networks mentioned regular meetings, workshops or other types of conferences or match-making events for networking as part of their normal functions. Bringing people and ideas together from science, policy and society and ways to strengthen the science-policy interface in different ways such as helping make science questions policy relevant and vice-a-versa were mentioned as some objectives. Activities such as lobbying or helping influence policy development were brought up especially by NGOs. Only one organisation mentioned that it also helps fund activities of others.

Disciplinary focus and knowledge

The majority of the networks interviewed described themselves as somehow either scientific or academic networks. This was also largely reflected in the composition of the participants and members of the networks (see next section). Many networks, also ones not claiming to be academic ones, mentioned that they aimed to be multi- or transdisciplinary and saw this as their strength. Only a couple of networks specified that they tend to gather people from a certain discipline such as social sciences, more common was to gather multidisciplinary people around certain topics so as to approach and gather information on the topic from various angles. Compiling and producing new knowledge and research were the aim of many of the networks. Also provision of training of methods to gather or synthesize knowledge or other technical or methodological training was mentioned as was training on how to communicate and disseminate research. Some networks had created platforms or databases to share and synthesize research and knowledge. The exchange of knowledge, networking around knowledge so to speak, can be said to have been the most common characteristic of the networks interviewed.

Figure 8. Word cloud showing key terms related to the major aims and functions of the interviewed networks

Membership

As the word cloud above also shows, the word “members” was mentioned often when speaking about the objectives and functions. Naturally, a network is not a network without members, and the members can have both active roles i.e. being the ones who produce the research or knowledge that moves in the networks, or more passive roles as participants in the events of the network or receiving information via newsletters, etc. Members or partners could also be individual people or whole organisations (fig. 9). The networks we interviewed usually had a diverse membership. Only 8 networks involved only one or two different types of actors, and in seven cases these were individual scientists or research and education bodies. The rest of the networks engaged at least 3 different types of actors, while 7 of them engaged the full spectrum of actors. How networks keep track of their participants or

partners and what size the networks are were not asked. As mentioned earlier, some of the networks had other networks or associations as their participants; this might make tracking membership even more challenging.

Figure 9. Different type of actors involved in the membership of the interviewed networks

The fact that the networks we interviewed were mainly research projects or thematic networks around certain topics largely explains why researchers or research bodies are most heavily represented among the memberships. Many of the EU funded projects have consortia that include also SMEs, NGOs and other types of partners, but researchers tend to dominate the consortia. Some networks do not have formal memberships, partners or participants but rather might consider also users of, for example a platform they have created as partners or participants. The actions and roles of the different partners and participants may vary a lot and is hard to evaluate, since few elaborated on this during the interviews. Also whether restrictions or requirements to participation of some sort apply or how members are chosen would be interesting to follow up on. Only one of the NGOs specifically mentioned that being a research organisation is not enough to become a member, rather members have to be action-oriented as well. Consultants or other types of experts were most commonly mentioned as “other” participants of the network.

Governance structure and decision-making mechanisms

The most common governance structure was that of a network governed by its participants and second most common a network governed by an administrative body established or elected by partners of the networks (fig. 10). In some cases, even though the network would have a type of administrative organisation, interviewees would find that the governing of the core activities happens via the participants whereas the administrative organisation would be in charge more of management issues such as budget, etc.

Figure 10. Governance structure of the networks interviewed⁵

The majority of the networks had regular meetings, an annual General Assembly most commonly, in which participants had the power to vote on the most important issues including the composition of the Board (Executive Board) or other bodies, such as council or steering committee for example, and the President and vice-president. In some cases, especially smaller organisations, all of the members could have been in the council or board, but more commonly each country or organisation had one or two representatives in the board. The board could also receive advice from an external Advisory Board of some type, usually related to how to improve sustainability, develop the business side of the network or related to a certain scientific topic that required outside expertise or consultancy. The power of the elected members of the executive board or other body varied. Liability was generally in the hands of the administrative or managing organisation. Some interviewees especially stressed the bottom-up type structure of their organisation and mentioned it as strength as well.

The project-type networks also tended to have some sort of advisory board, steering committee and general assembly. Despite members or partners having equal rights or power, often there would be people that were more active and formed a type of core group that would guide the project forward, sometimes even in a rather informal way. In projects, a distinction between who makes the scientific decisions and who the administrative ones was also mentioned once.

As mentioned, many of especially the larger networks additionally had committees or working groups which would often have their own, lighter, governance structure below the structure of the “head” network. Some networks also mentioned certain national laws under which they operated and also the power of governmental organizations to guide their actions or have certain requirements and for example the power also to appoint members. One organisation also mentioned that it does not have any external bodies due to the sensitivity of the innovations or work that they do.

As mentioned above, the general assembly was for many networks also the place where members could vote and thus make decisions on topical issues also related to the direction, functions and priorities of the network. Whether consensus was required for decisions to pass also varied, but generally a majority vote was sufficient. Who or what body decided on what types of issues varied among the networks, sometimes making it difficult to identify the network’s decision-making model with one of the suggested synthetic types (fig. 11).

⁵ Two of the interviewees chose a combination of two synthetic governance models, saying that their network is governed by a more complex structure of lead and administrative bodies.

Figure 11. Types of decision making models of the interviewed networks

Strategic decisions were generally made with everyone (i.e. through a voting at the general assembly), whereas how to implement the decisions was often left in the hands of a few. Transparency and accountability were mentioned as important aspects of decision-making. Suggestions and propositions could usually be made by anyone, brought forth sometimes by individuals or by member organisations who had prepared them among, e.g. national members. The ways propositions were dealt with was quite standard via discussion and, depending on the issue, via voting. Also different types of iterative processes where issues went through several rounds of discussion and modification were mentioned. One network also said that it would wish to include also outsiders or users, a type of crowd-sourcing, especially in the formation of topics and interests and to ensure quality and relevance of research and the issues at hand.

Funding

Approximately half of the networks collect a membership fee from either individual members or member organizations (fig. 12). Some of the networks said that they do face problems of members claiming that the fee is too high or being against raising the fees. Other organisations mentioned that their fees are mainly nominal, but even so might hinder some small organisations from becoming members. In some cases, the fee depended on the budget of the member organisation and sometimes it was the same for all members.

When asked about challenges related to funding, surprisingly many said that people or organisations often neglect to pay their membership fees. The networks that mainly run on membership fees also felt the fluctuation of the number of members as somewhat impacting their activities as steady income was not assured. Diversifying the funding base was mentioned as important to strengthen sustainability and adapting to new or changing conditions in the funding structures. This is also indicated by the fact that almost half of the networks (n=11) already try to diversify their revenue sources and therefore selected more than 1 from the options listed. Probably the most important challenge faced by the networks is that funds are often insufficient. Covering the costs of members attending important meetings or conferences was also a struggle for many networks and the networks had different principles about how to handle these costs. Also finding ways to promote the value added that would justify the fees and grow the activities to become more attractive was sometimes found difficult. Status,

being or not being a legal entity or other reasons for not qualifying for certain type of funding also impacted the funding models of the networks.

Figure 12. Dominant funding sources of the interviewed networks

Many of the networks had more than one kind of funding model, for instance they could have project funding and simultaneously also receive donations or other types of contributions and fees. Most strictly funding from only one source was apparent in the EU-projects that got their funding from one main source via, for example, H2020 or FP7 funds, but even many of the projects mentioned some type of support or additional small funding from, e.g., private companies or governmental organisations depending on the activity. A few of the EU projects said that they have more tasks and work than funding, so expectations and resources did not go hand in hand. They also often mentioned the “life after project funding” as one of their network’s challenges. Some of the projects had managed to keep an active informal post-project network going.

Only a handful of the organisations mentioned specifically that they are non-profits, even though many of them are. Additionally, only one mentioned that they also generate revenues by doing some type of work, usually consultancy.

Strengths and challenges of the networks

Many of the attributes mentioned as objectives and functions were seen also as the strengths of the networks. Table 6 shows the most commonly mentioned strengths; networking and relationships and interdisciplinarity being the most popular ones. Uniqueness in methods or ways of working and working in niche-areas also came out as strengths by some of the networks. These were seen as ways to build the added value and standing out. Interestingly, longevity and continuity as building reputation was mentioned by networks that had worked in the field for decades but also by projects or organisations that had existed only for a few years. This might say something about the expected life span of networks nowadays.

Table 6. Key strengths of the interviewed networks

<p>Multi-disciplinarity, knowledge and expertise</p>	<p>“It is a very multidisciplinary project, thus involves many scientists from different disciplines working together, bringing new ideas” “The key strength is this knowledge base itself, and the chance to exchange this knowledge and learn from each other”</p>
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Relationships and bringing people together, stakeholder engagement	“Extremely well established network of relations to European level decision-makers” “The overall approach and know-how of stakeholder engagement is also a strength of the network”
Reputation, transparency, longevity and credibility	“Additionally it is a very well-known organisation and has a strong reputation” “continuity of activities, dedicated team working on a continuous basis, team including a communication expert striving to be credible and transparent in our work”
Size and (geographical) coverage Small – flexibility, productiveness Big – large diverse membership, creative and lots of expertise	“Meetings are very productive due to the relatively small membership” “Global network that is able to engage at various scales” “X has a strong community, which is its most valuable resource (1500 members now), super brain”
Communications and user-friendliness	“communication experts who work on making the ongoing projects more attractive and easily understandable to larger audiences” “Standard design and user interface”

Interestingly, in the challenges section some of the things networks had mentioned as strengths appeared as challenges in other networks. Naturally, for example, the coordination of a smaller network might be simpler and showing the added value of bigger networks with more capacities and resources might be easier. As many networks work on a voluntary basis, getting people to commit was also challenging. Funding and sustainability were challenges especially for the project-based networks which have a set budget and lifespan. Tensions within the networks were also mentioned, occasionally related to differing views of the objectives of the network or not being used to dealing with different types of sectors and actors, for example fitting the roles of researchers, SMEs and NGOs in EU-projects. There are surely issues in which the networks could benefit from each other strengths to overcome some of the challenges.

Table 7. Key challenges of the interviewed networks

Making an impact on policy	“Difficulties to transform scientific results to something with societal value, like policy. To make this into policy you need the government involved, which is not necessarily easy or always feasible.”
Funding and growth Finding new sources of funding and funds to grow the network	“Funding is the major challenge: balancing the capacity needed and the funding available. - Broadening the activities and increasing the number of employees is desirable, but this would need more money. However, without more staff members (more capacities to fund raising and project proposal writing) it is difficult to bring in more money.”
Getting people to invest time Showing the added value of the network Competing with other networks for members	“Convincing the members to contribute more than minimum, to find new members” “There are more and more emerging new societies, differentiation is more difficult – potential to loose members”
Tensions within the network Related to personal/organisational tensions and coordination Related to the scientific work and research	“There are altogether 37 partners involved in the project, administration and coordination of such a large consortium is challenging. Also the topic is quite broad, so coordination in terms of scientific work is also challenging sometimes”
Communication	“Communication – messages should be delivered to a wider audience, mainstreaming is not yet effective enough”
Adapting to change and flexibility	“The structure of X makes change / adaptation to new/different conditions a challenging task”
External relations and stakeholder engagement	“how to engage citizens effectively (strategies have to fit different peoples and cultures)”

5.2 Networks' expectations, concerns and needs regarding EKLIPSE

Potential added values of the EKLIPSE mechanism as perceived by networks

Question 8 of the interview guide asked respondents about their expectations towards the EKLIPSE mechanism. In most interviews this question helped respondents to consider their actual and potential collaborations with EKLIPSE and resulted in a deep (and sometimes critical) reflection. However, the question was somewhat difficult to answer for those network representatives which are yet indirectly related to science and policy dialogues in the field of biodiversity and ecosystem services. The actual situation of the networks also influenced if the respondents could identify any a priori expectations towards EKLIPSE. For example, one of the networks interviewed is currently searching new objectives and renewing its mission, and thinking about new collaborations is beyond the actual capacities. Another network is in the phase of harvesting results, therefore they put more emphasis now on dissemination instead of establishing new linkages. Qualitative content analysis of the answers revealed 6 major types of expectations, as detailed below.

The first and most populated type of expectations (mentioned altogether by 17 interviewees) relates to the **improvement of science-policy interactions**; as one respondent stated, EKLIPSE should “[provide] a process through which policy problems can be transformed into scientific problems and vice versa.” Responses suggest that EKLIPSE could help operationalizing scientific knowledge, generating simple enough but robust results, and translating them into key messages and public statements. This is very much in line with questionnaire results, which suggest that policy support is one of the key expectations towards EKLIPSE. As one interviewee stated, “simple messages are needed to approach decision-makers, as they have 5 minutes maximum for you.” Getting into closer relationship with policy-makers is considered the most efficient if there is a common and standardized way of interfacing. This could result in policy-makers' increased awareness of environmental issues and higher willingness to support research on such topics, as well as more direct feedback from policy to science and therefore more problem-oriented research projects.

The second most important expectation (mentioned by 15 interviewees) focuses on the **identification and engagement of key stakeholders** both at the EU, regional, and national level. Some of the interviewed networks face the challenge of establishing links with practitioner communities in different countries, and they consider that the multi-level embeddedness of a network organization is a critical success factor. While they encourage EKLIPSE to build these multi-level linkages, they also hope to benefit from this, and broaden their own networks through the collaboration with EKLIPSE. As one interviewee said, EKLIPSE could “help organizations to reach out and networking at the national level and this way link together interested parties.” Whom should be engaged is not clear, though. Many interviewees said that “relevant” and “interested” parties, “key people” and “important decision-makers” should be brought together by EKLIPSE, however who they are was rarely specified. EU-level decision-makers in general, and DG Agri and DG Environment in particular were mentioned by one respondent, while others said that the private sector (business actors) and the civil society is also important to get engaged. Whether the civil society should be brought into the dialogue via representative organizations (NGOs) or via individual citizens was a contested issue. This underlines findings from the online survey, questioning that it is the citizen who should be directly involved in the science-policy-society dialogue.

An important expectation towards EKLIPSE is to **mobilize available expertise** and create and use an **inclusive knowledge base** (mentioned by 15 respondents). Some of the networks who actually face the disengagement or volatility of their members expect that the mechanism provided by EKLIPSE could provide motivation for their membership to get engaged more actively with the network again by

bringing in a new perspective – namely the opportunity to directly contribute to decision-making through acting at the SPI. Others offered explicitly that their membership can be used as a knowledge hub, and critical and cutting edge knowledge can be generated by integrating these different sources of knowledge. This however needs novel approaches to knowledge integration and synthesis, and probably requires capacity building within scientific and expert communities, exchanging opportunities, and learning about policy processes. Concerns were raised in terms of maintaining the engagement level on the longer run, to make possible that *“knowledge-holders don’t disappear after EKLIPSE ends.”* These findings nicely fit to the questionnaire results, where many of the respondents requested for support in knowledge generation and integration.

Effectively disseminate results and reach the target audience was mentioned by 9 interviewees, as the following citation indicates: *“[It is important to] create a mechanism through which knowledge created by projects like X reaches the relevant stakeholders/policy-makers/investors.”* Some interviewees explicitly offered their own communication channels (e.g. regular conferences or online platforms) to spread information and receive feedback. It was also discussed how communication could be made effective – and capacity building was mentioned in terms of communicating scientific results -, because *“[m]essages should be able to be delivered clearly and quickly to persuade decision-makers, which means that very simple and meaningful messages are needed disseminate it.”*

Some respondents (n=6) mentioned long-term general expectations concerning the **future sustainability of EKLIPSE**. As one of them stated, it would be crucial *“to move from a “paper based organisation” to an actual network, with buildings, infrastructure, set goals and agenda, something like the European Space Agency, but adjusted to the needs biodiversity and ecosystem resources have.”* Foresight activities and the identification of emerging new topics and research needs is also important to secure the long term position of the mechanism. However, the potential of merging with other existing interfaces, and building legacy on a shared platform was also mentioned as a potential long term strategy.

This drives us to another expectation, raised by another 6 interviewees, suggesting that EKLIPSE should **join forces with existing networks and avoid any duplications**. EKLIPSE is expected to link up with other networks, and expanding the interrelations, which was also claimed by the survey respondents. This is also important for those networks which are not yet so active in the field of biodiversity and ecosystem services – identifying the gaps where they could contribute and creating synergies would be a good step forward. Altogether 10 interviewees mentioned concrete ideas for potential collaboration or talked about actual collaboration between their network and EKLIPSE.

Beside their expectations, a quarter of the interviewees also talked about their **concerns** regarding EKLIPSE. The most debated feature of EKLIPSE is the potential overlap with other existing interfaces. As one of the interviewees stated: *“Why should you start from scratch? Why for instance not pursue the same goals through an already established organization which has similar interests and could expand them?”* Also the difficulties of knowledge synthesis (from a methodological point of view) and knowledge dissemination (creating clear but robust messages, reaching to the target audience) were mentioned. As a more general challenge, two interviewees mentioned the regional differences within Europe (especially the gap between CEE countries and the more developed regions of Europe in terms of the strength of the civil society as well as the attention paid and funds allocated to environmental issues), which has to be taken into account. A possible solution for this could be to create a system of country representatives for EKLIPSE as suggested by one respondent, and also mentioned by another one recalling good experiences with such a system.

Gaps in knowledge and capacities

Question 9 focused on the capacity and knowledge gaps faced by networks. 5 respondents said they have no particular gaps in capacities, the rest of the responses is summed in table 8. **Lack of resources** (both human and financial resources) (n=9) and **capacity and knowledge gaps in communication** (n=8) seem to be the key challenges for many of the networks interviewed. **Lack of knowledge with thematic foci** (esp. knowledge on certain aspects of biodiversity, knowledge on uncertainty and knowledge on policy processes) was also prominent in some of the interviews. **Lack of knowledge on policy processes** was interlinked with limited capacities to effectively act at the science-policy interface. Challenges to increase or better engage the membership, and to broaden the geographical scale of the network were mentioned by 3 interviewees, and another 3 talked about general capacity gaps in networking, especially related to the engagement of different sectors.

Table 8. Capacity and knowledge gaps of the interviewed networks

	Capacity gaps	Knowledge gaps
Hard conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Human resources (both administrative staff and membership) - Financial resources (lack of funds, insufficient fundraising) - Incentive structures for scientists and experts 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lack of data on biodiversity and ecosystem services - Economics and social sciences of biodiversity and ecosystem services of marine environments - Understanding uncertainty - Understanding the policy cycle and legal structures (taken into account country-specific or regional differences)
Soft conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Communication with stakeholders (policy-makers, civil society) and the use of various media channels - Networking across sectors (e.g. engaging SMEs) and across geographical regions (e.g. broader geographical scope) - Creating further partnerships 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Multi- and interdisciplinary work and a common language for different disciplines

The comparison of capacity and knowledge gaps listed by survey respondents and interviewees shows some overlap regarding the lack of knowledge on thematic issues and policy processes, and the capacity gaps in networking. However, new gaps were identified by the interviewees such as the lack of human and financial resources, and the capacity and knowledge gaps in communication. This deviation might show the differences between individual and organizational perspectives, the latter focusing more on structural difficulties and gaps.

Most efficient ways to fill capacity gaps

Networks interviewed usually use a diversified approach to capacity building, and combine various different tools and approaches depending on their audience, the type of capacity gaps to fill as well as the time and financial limitations. In accordance with questionnaire results, face-to-face interactive events such as **trainings** and **workshops** (n=12 and n=7 respectively), and conferences and open access publications (n=7) were mentioned as popular formats for capacity building. It is important, however, to find the right format in the given situation – as one of our interviewees said “[in] the beginning of the project workshops were quite effective (3 days, incl. 60-80 people with different backgrounds), but now this setting is not really suitable to share specific knowledge or improve specific skills. To this end, trainings for smaller audiences might be more effective.” On the other hand, there is a significant difference in the perception of **webinars**. Only 3 survey respondents mentioned webinars among the

effective capacity building tools, while 11 interviewees mentioned it as a tool they use themselves. It was acknowledged by some of the interviewees that webinars mostly work for broader audiences (i.e. at EU or even higher levels), and that this tool is mostly used by networks if they would like to go beyond their regular audience. However, how effective webinars are in terms of reaching a wider audience is unclear. Questionnaire results in this respect have an important message, indicating that webinars are not so popular among individual interfacers, and therefore might have a limited capacity to spread information.

In addition to the more common formats listed above, interviewees (n=5) also suggested **twinning, mentoring and joint field experiments** as effective ways to fill specific gaps in knowledge or capacities. Best practices were also shared for this category. For instance, one of the interviewed learned societies runs each year a small grant scheme to support collaboration among its individual members, who have to form small working groups around a major objective (this can be an original research, a dissemination activity, knowledge exchange, etc.) and apply for the grant with a written plan. According to their experience, this small grant scheme allows the members to visit each other, and create a joint action with real-life impacts. Another best practice focuses on students' engagement by offering a mentoring in science communication (e.g. writing blogs) to the successful applicants. **Matchmaking** events were mentioned by 4 interviewees, highlighting that they can be very effective if different sectors (policy, science, business) are invited in equal numbers. **Thematic discussion groups**, inviting a broad and diverse audience were mentioned 3 times, while **hackathon** (a dynamic and creative two-day event, usually engaging diverse knowledge-holders and focusing on real-life problem-solving) was listed by one respondent, acknowledging that hackathon can be a very effective format to generate action and find real-life creative (mostly technology-oriented) solution to a problem.

Besides listing tools for capacity building and giving best practice examples, interviewees also shared some general comments about limiting and enabling factors of successful capacity building. Two of the interviewees acknowledged that the success of their capacity building events lies in the fact that they have developed detailed guidelines that are adapted and continuously improved from year to year. It is therefore worth considering that EKLIPSE should develop a similar guidance system. Another issue, raised by representatives of NGOs, relates to financial limitations. As one of them described, *"Having more money is the key. Any of the above listed capacity building activities might be useful, but lack of capacities can only be filled if financial circumstances are improved."* This suggests that capacity building targeting the civil sphere must be much more sensitive towards (in)equalities and should apply an inclusive approach. This is especially important if regional differences (also mentioned in the previous section) are to be managed.

Preferred communication channels

Networks interviewed use a huge variety of communication tools. E-mails, both personal and generalized, were mentioned by all interviewees as one of the most effective communication tools. Personalized e-mails were perceived as the most effective tool to trigger feedback from within the membership, while generalized e-mail were thought to be useful to spread information, as one interviewee stated: *"the more personalized the message, the better the response rate."* In some networks, questionnaires are used to gather feedback, and in networks that use this tool regularly, response rate used to be quite good.

Social media has an increasing relevance, especially as the membership gets younger. Mainly twitter and facebook were mentioned, although for twitter a regional imbalance is perceived by some of the interviewees, suggesting that twitter is less frequently used in CEE countries. Interviewees consider social media mainly as a marketing tool that provides good visibility, while its potential for true

engagement is questioned by some. A limitation was also mentioned by one of the interviewees, revealing that experts from non-English-speaking countries might have a disadvantage in online interactions, especially if they use their native languages in their country specific organizations (applies mostly for CEE countries).

Website news stream and newsletter is a popular communication channel to spread information, although its effectiveness is questioned by some of the interviewees, stating that the newsletter is already old-fashioned compared to more interactive social media channels. Online meetings (e.g. via skype or gotomeeting) are usually used for internal communication. In addition, some interviewees revealed that e-conferences can be useful to engage a wider audience in discussing a specific topic. Face-to-face contacts, personal communications, phone calls were also mentioned as important ways of networking and communicating. Some interviewees even suggested that maintaining good personal relations, although time consuming, but key for the success of the network. Less frequently used communication channels included videos (mentioned by two interviewees as a more interesting format to share knowledge and engage a wider audience) and written reports and briefings, which are effective if there is an active and well targeted audience (i.e. researchers in a scientific discipline or sector specific policy-makers).

5.3 Networks' contribution potential in organised Science –Policy –Society interface

The vast majority of the network representatives interviewed recognised the growing need for organised Science-Policy-Society interface regarding biodiversity and ecosystem services. To identify their potential to contribute to such efforts, through the EKLIPSE mechanism or other structured procedures with similar goals, the networks' representatives were asked to evaluate the capacity and interest of their organisation/network/project to undertake specific contributing roles (EKLIPSE D5.1, 2017) linked to their core activities. Figure 13 provides a general assessment of these potential contributions to organised Science-Policy-Society interface efforts. The results indicate that, overall, the representatives of the networks interviewed feel more comfortable to provide contributions related to thematic or/and methodological expertise, as well as acknowledge their role as a potential knowledge hub, rather than provide management support or act as evaluators of the process. This outcome seems to be directly connected with the nature of the participating networks (mainly scientific networks/projects/organisation, which have direct access to thematic knowledge, innovative methodologies, organised structures of knowledge exchange, etc. as well as with their structure (projects/networks facing operational challenges) which may not allow the undertaking of long-term responsibilities as is management.

Figure 13. General assessment of the networks' interest to undertake alternative roles in EKLIPSE mechanism or other organised Science-Policy-Society interface effort.

5.4 Networking relationships and liaisons (diagram based on the last question)

The final question to the interviewees was aiming at identifying their networks' relationships with a number of organisations/hubs which were reported in the *KNEU* project as having significant impact on science-policy interaction concerning biodiversity and ecosystem services in Europe. This investigation aims to identify the direct collaborative relationships between different organisations/ networks/ projects/ hubs, in order to better understand how the Network of Networks can be structured and function, as well as to identify those networks that are better situated to act as liaison point/ ambassadors of EKLIPSE activities and of the importance of Science-Policy-Interface regarding biodiversity and ecosystem services.

To achieve better understanding of these networking relationships and liaisons, three levels of analysis was performed:

- A general assessment of the level of collaboration between the 19 key organisations/hubs identified and the networks interviewed, distinguishing between “no knowledge of the existence of the organisation/hub” (1) to “strong collaboration” (4), as presented in figure 14.
- The visualization of the sub-networks of collaboration created around each one of the 19 key organisations/hubs (placed at the centre of each diagram) and in relation to the interviewed network, distinguishing between the networks which declare to have strong collaborations with each organisation/hub (inner circle) and the networks which have minor collaboration with the same organisation/hub (placed at the perimeter of the diagram) (available only for internal project use).
- The representation of each of the networks interviewed in connection with the 19 key organisations identified (minor and major collaborations equally taken into account) to evaluate each network's capacity to act as a liaising point between other organisations/ projects/ networks, in different contexts (available only for internal project use).

Regarding the general assessment of the level of relationships between the identified organisations/hubs and the networks interviewed (figure 14), it is not surprising that most networks have strong collaborations with different Directorates of the European Commission, as well as with organisations connected to the United Nations. DG RES is the most popular organisation in terms of collaboration with the networks interviewed, mainly due to two reasons: a) the majority of the networks interviewed are mainly active in research and b) DG RES has a transdisciplinary character, bringing together research networks coming from natural, economic, social scientific and other disciplines. As it is obvious from the diagram, the levels of collaboration between the 19 key hubs vary significantly. This fact can be, of course, attributed to the different structure, operation level and operation functionality of each of the hubs. For instance, both EC and UN are significant sources of funding, which makes them popular collaborators, but this doesn't necessarily place them at the best position to act as liaison points between other networks, because of their governing structure and their necessary bureaucratic nature. Other organisations/hubs, as NGOs with global and EU action, or organisations as IUCN, GBIF, the European Environmental Bureau, etc., although seemingly having smaller collaborative networks around them, they may have more flexibility, as well as interest, in acting as key networking points regarding Science-Policy-Society interface.

Not all networks/projects/organisations have the same interest or need to act as networking points to facilitate their activities, but there are certain organisations which have both high interest on and capability of doing so. Although EKLIPSE is and always will be open to any and all collaborations which promote Science-Policy-Society interface regarding biodiversity and ecosystem services, it aims to

specifically collaborate with networks which have high outreach potential, to create opportunities for bilateral growth to identify organisations which can act as ambassadors of the EKLIPSE aims and goals. Particular importance should be given to collaborations with organisations which can offer an opening to networks with focus on the economic and social science disciplines, which is very much needed to achieve EKLIPSE goals.

Figure 14. General assessment of the liaison of Networks with key organisations working with biodiversity and ecosystem services.

6 Key findings and steps forward

The EKLIPSE Deliverable 5.2 aimed at exploring how existing networks function and interact at the science-policy-society interface, and identifying room for collaboration and capacity building to improve interactions. Based on these results, the Deliverable will contribute to further develop the EKLIPSE Network of Networks.

The study revealed that existing networks and their membership are already engaged in science-policy-society interactions, and EKLIPSE has to find its place within the actual landscape to be able to build an effective mechanism. Some survey respondents and also some of the interviewees struggled with seeing the added values of EKLIPSE, or the way this NoN differs from other science-policy-society interfaces. In addition, as funding is an important limitation to many of the existing networks, there is naturally a competitive situation perceived in the field. This highlights that EKLIPSE should have a more active communication with existing networks, and should create a dialogue or a negotiation process through which collaborations can be formalized and overlaps can be avoided. Additionally, EKLIPSE should clearly communicate controversial issues of power, legitimacy and transparency when the idea of merging with / integrating EKLIPSE into an existing organization emerges. Results also suggest that general communication channels (such as newsletters, websites, generalized e-mails) are not suitable for meaningful engagement. Personalized e-mails are more effective, but to really engage relevant actors and build trust personal communication (via phone or face-to-face meetings) is of high importance.

Many networks realized potential in the NoN, especially in terms of creating an open and inclusive knowledge base, increase / incentivize membership and support impactful research. The networks interviewed present variant capacity and willingness to undertake different roles in the science-policy-society interface. It is up to EKLIPSE (and the future mechanism) to identify the appropriate manner and incentives to create long-lasting and fruitful collaborations towards this direction. There are multiple networks identified which can act as liaisons or ambassadors of the SPI regarding biodiversity and ecosystem services. EKLIPSE should focus on expanding collaborations with networks which can provide access to other disciplines beyond the environmental sciences (such as ecological economics, environmental social sciences), as well as to organisations which can expand collaboration with society (NGOs).

Capacities perceived as necessary to be improved include knowledge generation and sharing, understanding policy processes, and communication. Communication was mentioned many times as a crucial but oftentimes limited capacity of networks and individuals, either because there are not enough financial resources or because there is a lack of expertise. Communication habits are changing, the younger generation being much more familiar with social media and online tools, while many of the established actors still rely on more traditional ways of informing and being informed. The wide geographical coverage is also challenging, as communication tools are not equally popular across European countries (e.g. Twitter is not frequently used in CEE context), and language barriers might also appear. These findings have an important message to the mechanism. The communication strategy of EKLIPSE should be diversified. To engage networks, more personal communication channels and tools should be used. To engage individual actors, communication tools should be diversified according to the type of actors involved. To create equal opportunities to participate across Europe, either discussions in native languages should be supported (e.g. through a network of country

representatives), or targeted support should be provided to networks/individuals representing less well-off countries. By creating a successful and effective communication strategy, EKLIPSE could become a role model, and could support other existing networks, in terms of how to effectively share information and engage membership. This would be a highly valued service to some of the networks and individuals.

Identifying and engaging the diversity of stakeholders, relevant to a certain issue or decision, was highlighted by research participants as a key expectation towards EKLIPSE. This suggests that EKLIPSE should develop and apply a toolbox that enables expert working groups and EKLIPSE members in general to reach out to multiple audiences, which might vary case-by-case (request-by-request). So far EKLIPSE has been engaging with its wider audience through its online forum (KNOCK) focusing more on expert and practitioner communities, and the science cafés focusing more on the general public; while identifying key stakeholders have been resting with the expert working groups. Making stakeholder engagement more direct and lively, targeted approaches might be needed that are tailor-made to each request through the process of scoping.

Capacity building tools, used by research participants, are highly diverse, indicating that different tools are effective in different situations and for different audiences. Here again some of the respondents mentioned financial resources as a limitation, which shows that the EKLIPSE capacity building calls can be of huge relevance. Besides these calls, webinars form an important part of EKLIPSE capacity building activities. Results warns us, however, that webinars might not be attractive enough to some actors, or at least individual players at the science-policy-society interface do not participate such forms of capacity building frequently. We suggest that the role (target audience, topic, and incentive system) of webinars should be carefully considered, and options to make them more attractive should be identified (e.g. develop them into online courses – MOOCS – to receive credits in higher education, or provide additional mentoring to support more in-depth learning of the participants).

Although several important dimensions of the NoN has been explored by this study, some questions remained open and needs further investigation and reflection on behalf of the EKLIPSE team. These are the followings:

- The networks have quite similar and standard/conventional governing and decision-making structures, but (informally) some members are always more active and others passive. It is not entirely clear yet what this implies for participating/being part of a NoN. Is a NoN possible or is it mostly just individuals that participate in these types or networks if it is on a voluntary/pro-bono basis? Theoretically sound and empirically justified reflections on the platform vs. network vs. hybrid approach would be timely and could help support the development of the future mechanism.
- EKLIPSE aims to create a science-policy-society interface, and has a work package devoted to societal engagement. It is however unclear yet, whether society should be engaged through representative organizations, or by inviting citizens. Most of the responses favored the engagement of civil society organizations, but we have to acknowledge that organizations that have experience with direct citizen engagement were only marginally represented in this study (mainly because we could not access them). The only organization interviewed which engages citizens by principle shared good experiences with working with citizens, and revealed that direct engagement of the public helps to raise awareness and foster action. However, this requires a different approach (more action-oriented, more local and more context-dependent)

than the one used so far by EKLIPSE. Hence, the future role and model of societal engagement has to be discussed and improved by the consortium.

7 Acknowledgement

We are grateful to all the respondents and interviewees who devoted their time to answer our questions. The research design and the draft report was circulated among the EKLIPSE consortium members, and we thank for all the valuable comments to the project team, especially to Bálint Balázs, Györgyi Bela, Estelle Balian, Alexandra Lux, Marion Mehring, Riikka Paloniemi, Isabel Sousa Pinto, Juliette Young, Marie Vandewalle, and Allan Watt.

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9 Annexes

9.1 Original long questionnaire

EKLIPSE questionnaire for network representatives

The EKLIPSE project is asking for your help in answering a short questionnaire regarding actors' networks related to biodiversity and ecosystem services.

EKLIPSE is an EU-funded project that started in February 2016 (for more information, please visit our website: <http://www.eclipse-mechanism.eu/>). The project has five main objectives:

- To set up a light and transparent governance model for a self-sustainable support mechanism for evidence-based policy on biodiversity and ecosystem services in the EU;
- To coordinate innovative and transparent approaches for science, policy and societal actors to jointly provide evidence leading to better informed decision-making;
- To promote the effective engagement of all society, research and policy actors in multidisciplinary and transdisciplinary consultations to jointly identify research priorities and emerging issues related to biodiversity and ecosystem services;
- To encourage societal debate on and engagement with relevant policy and research on biodiversity and ecosystem services;
- To engage better with those networks whose knowledge has a key potential impact on biodiversity and ecosystem services.

This last objective is key to improving the science-policy-society interface. The major aim of this questionnaire is to engage existing networks, and improve the functioning of the Network of Networks (NoN).

To reach this aim, the questionnaire focusses on two key aspects:

- How do existing networks work and which challenges do they face?
- What can EKLIPSE do for your network? What do you see as your potential contribution to the Network of Networks?

The questionnaire is structured around these two aspects. The first part focusses on your experiences within your own network, the second one focusses on your ideas for EKLIPSE and science-policy interfaces in general.

*With **Networks** we refer to different kinds of "organized exchange" – e.g. informal thematic networks, formal networks of institutions, learned societies, NGOs etc. – so please understand this term quite broadly when answering the questions.*

Filling in the questionnaire requires approximately 40 minutes. All data will be securely stored, and anonymized. The data from the questionnaires will not be shared outside of the EKLIPSE consortium. EKLIPSE will use the results of the questionnaires in scientific research, in developing science-policy communication and to feedback to networks. One initial opportunity for feedback will be the first EKLIPSE conference planned in Brussels on the 7/8th December 2016. We will send you more detailed information soon.

We are grateful for your collaboration!

Before filling in the questionnaire please provide some basic contact details of the network you represent. This allows us to contact your network with updates on project related news, calls for expertise and capacity building opportunities etc., disseminated by EKLIPSE.

- Name of the network your represent:
- Name and e-mail address of the coordinator(s) of your network:
- Name and e-mail address of key contact person(s) (if different from the coordinator) of your network:

Part A: Questions related to your own network

Please note that by **Networks** we refer to different kinds of “organized exchange” – e.g. informal thematic networks, formal networks of institutions, learned societies, NGOs etc. – so please understand this term quite broadly.

*A1. What are the major **objectives/functions** of your network? Please provide some keywords or a short explanation!*

*A2. What is the **governance structure** of your network? Please choose the most suitable one from the governance structures listed below. If your network has a completely different structure, please choose the ‘other’ option, and give a short explanation.*

1. Network governed by its participants (no separate and/or unique governance entity exists)
2. Network governed by a lead organization (major activities and key decisions rest with the central organization which taken the leading role)
3. Network governed by an administrative organization, established by partners of the network
4. Other, please specify:

*A3. Who are your **partners/participants**? Please choose the types of membership most typical for your network from the list below (you can choose more than one option).*

1. Individual researchers
2. Individual practitioners (e.g. landscape managers, engineers)
3. Business actors (e.g. entrepreneurs, companies, representatives of business interest groups)
4. Research or educational bodies (e.g. research institutes, universities)
5. Representatives of non-governmental organizations
6. Representatives of governmental organizations (e.g. legislator or administrative bodies)
7. Other, please specify:
8. Other, please specify:
9. Other, please specify:

A4. How are decisions made in your network? Please choose the type of decision making processes most typical for your network from the list below.

1. Decisions are solely made by the governing body/organization in a centralized way.
2. Decision making follows a consultative model where the governing body/organization makes the decision, based on feedback received from within the membership.
3. Decisions are prepared (e.g. alternatives identified and compared) by the governing body/organization, while the final decisions are by the general assembly or equivalent institution.
4. Decisions are proposed/prepared on a voluntary basis by the membership, decisions are made by the general assembly or equivalent institution.
5. Other, please specify:

A4.1. If at the previous question you chose options 3 or 4 (acknowledging that there is a general assembly or similar institution in your network), please indicate **how frequently the general assembly (or equivalent institution) meets**:

- a. More than twice a year
- b. Twice a year
- c. Once a year
- d. Once in every 2 year
- e. Less frequently than once in every 2 year
- f. There is no general assembly or similar institutions in my network

A5. What is the **funding model** for your network? Please choose the types of funding sources most typical for your network from the list below (you can choose more than one option).

1. Payments/fees from individual members
2. Payments from member organizations
3. One main funding source, please specify (e.g. DG, governmental body etc.):
4. Contracts/ projects
5. Fundraising, please specify:
6. Other:

If possible please also provide some more explanation on the funding model of your network and challenges you face regarding funding.

The next two questions are about internal communication within your network. Please note that we ask separate questions about one-way communication (informing the members within your network – Question A6) and two-way communication (triggering feedback –Question A7).

A6. How effective are the following communication tools in your network in terms of **informing as many people as possible (one-way communication)**? Please choose those tools from the list below which are used by your network and rate them from 1 to 5 where 1 means not at all effective and 5 means very effective.

Tools (please tick the tools used in your network)		Please rate the tools applied in your network from 1 (not at all effective) to 5 (very effective)				
		1	2	3	4	5
<input type="checkbox"/>	Personalized e-mails					
<input type="checkbox"/>	General e-mails					
<input type="checkbox"/>	Newsletters or blog					
<input type="checkbox"/>	News on the network's own website					
<input type="checkbox"/>	RSS feeds					
<input type="checkbox"/>	Twitter					
<input type="checkbox"/>	Researchgate profile of your network					
<input type="checkbox"/>	LinkedIN profile of your network					
<input type="checkbox"/>	Facebook group of your network					
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other:					
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other:					
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other:					

A7. How effective are the following communication tools in your network in terms of **triggering feedback (two-way communication)**? Please choose those tools from the list below which are used by your network and rate them from 1 to 5 (1 meaning not at all effective, 5 very effective).

Tools (please tick the tools used in your network)		Please rate the tools applied in your network from 1 (not at all effective) to 5 (very effective)				
		1	2	3	4	5
<input type="checkbox"/>	Personalized e-mails					
<input type="checkbox"/>	General e-mails					
<input type="checkbox"/>	Newsletters or blog					
<input type="checkbox"/>	News on the network's own website					
<input type="checkbox"/>	RSS feeds					
<input type="checkbox"/>	Twitter					
<input type="checkbox"/>	Researchgate profile of your network					
<input type="checkbox"/>	LinkedIN profile of your network					
<input type="checkbox"/>	Facebook group of your network					
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other:					
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other:					
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other:					

A8. What **key strengths** do you think your network has? Please list 5 strengths at maximum.

A9. What **challenges** are your network facing? Please consider the following list of possible challenges and rate them on a 1-5 scale, where 1 means that the given aspect is not challenging at all, and 5 means the given aspect is highly challenging.

Aspects of network functioning	Please rate the following options: 1 means not challenging at all, 5 means very challenging				
Scientific quality of the work of member institutions or individuals.	1	2	3	4	5
Transparency concerning the information flow within the network.	1	2	3	4	5
Time that members devote to network related work.	1	2	3	4	5
Ethical infrastructure (including #####) within the network.	1	2	3	4	5
Network's external relationships (i.e. relations to policy-makers or specific interest groups)	1	2	3	4	5
Other challenges, if any, please specify					
Other challenges, if any, please specify					
Other challenges, if any, please specify					

Part B: Questions about your opinion on science-policy interfaces in general and EKLIPSE in particular.

Please note that by EKLIPSE **mechanism** we refer to the science-policy-society interface being developed in the EKLIPSE project to support evidence-informed decision-making affecting biodiversity and ecosystem services.

B1. What role would you like your network to take in the EKLIPSE project and future mechanism? Please consider the following options to engage with EKLIPSE and rate your network's interest from 1 to 3, where 1 refers to having no interest in certain roles, 2 refers to having potential interest but lacking knowledge and/or capacity to contribute, and 3 refers to actual interest and capability to fulfilling certain roles based on existing knowledge and capacity within our network.

Functions within EKLIPSE	1: no interest	2: possible interest but lack of knowledge/ capacity	3: actual interest based on existing knowledge/ capacity
Provision of thematic expertise	1	2	3
Provision of methodological expertise	1	2	3
Knowledge hub	1	2	3
Management support	1	2	3
Provision of data/information	1	2	3
Provision of tools and infrastructure	1	2	3
Capacity building	1	2	3
Communication	1	2	3
Society and policy interface	1	2	3
Think tank role	1	2	3
Foresight role	1	2	3
Evaluation of the work of the mechanism	1	2	3
Other role, please specify:			

Other role, please specify:	
Other role, please specify:	

B2. Which **capacities should be improved** in your network to be able to fulfill possible functions within EKLIPSE? (Please think of the functions you chosen at the second column of the previous question – Question B1).

B3. Which are the **most effective ways to fulfill capacity gaps** in your network (e.g. webinars, trainings, conferences, matchmaking events)? Please list no more than 5 possible ways of capacity building.

B4. How **essential** do you think this Network of Networks will be in terms of strengthening the different aspects of the science-policy-society interface?

The role of EKLIPSE in strengthening the interaction...	Not at all essential-----Very essential				
... between policy-makers and scientist	1	2	3	4	5
... between policy-makers and networks	1	2	3	4	5
... between policy-makers and civil society	1	2	3	4	5
... between networks and scientists	1	2	3	4	5
... between networks and civil society	1	2	3	4	5
... between civil society and scientists	1	2	3	4	5
The science-policy-society interface in general	1	2	3	4	5

B5. How important it is to **involve** the following actors in science-policy-society communication regarding biodiversity and ecosystem services at European scale? Please rate the specific actors listed below from 1 to 5 where 1 means not at all important to involve and 5 means extremely important to involve.

Actors to be involved	Not at all important-----Very important				
Natural scientists	1	2	3	4	5
Social scientists	1	2	3	4	5
Other scientists	1	2	3	4	5
Representatives for civil society	1	2	3	4	5
Citizens	1	2	3	4	5
Decision-makers at European scale	1	2	3	4	5
Decision-makers at national scale	1	2	3	4	5

Representatives of specific networks (please use the rows below to list specific networks you think necessary to involve, if any):					
-	1	2	3	4	5
-	1	2	3	4	5
-	1	2	3	4	5

B6. Below we list some networks/hubs that were reported in the KNEU project as having significant impact on science-policy interaction concerning biodiversity and ecosystem services in Europe. Please consider if your network has any direct or indirect links with the listed ones. Please feel free to add other networks that you think significant in this field.

Name of organization/network/project	I have not yet heard about it.	I have heard about it but not been involved.	My network have minor collaboration with it.	My network has strong collaboration with it.
COPA-COGECA	1	2	3	4
EEA (European Environmental Agency)	1	2	3	4
EEB (European Environmental Bureau)	1	2	3	4
EPBRS (European Platform for Biodiversity Research Strategy)	1	2	3	4
European Commission: DG Agri	1	2	3	4
European Commission: DG Environment	1	2	3	4
European Commission: DG Mare	1	2	3	4
European Commission: DG Research				
EU funded research projects on ecosystem services and biodiversity (e.g. BESAFE, ESMERALDA, LIBERATION, OpenNESS, OPERAs, QuESSA etc.)	1	2	3	4
EuroMarine (European Marine Research Network)	1	2	3	4
Future Earth / DIVERSITAS	1	2	3	4
GBIF (Global Biodiversity Information Facility)	1	2	3	4
Global and regional scientific assessments, such as IPCC, IPBES, TEEB, MA, CoML	1	2	3	4
ICES (International Council for the Exploration of the Sea)	1	2	3	4
International Conventions (e.g. the Bern Convention, CBD, Ramsar etc.)	1	2	3	4
International and European NGOs such as WWF, Birdlife, Greenpeace etc.	1	2	3	4
IUCN	1	2	3	4

JRC (Joint Research Centre of the European Commission)	1	2	3	4
UN and its organizations (e.g. UNEP, FAO, UNESCO, UNDP)	1	2	3	4
Other:	1	2	3	4
Other:	1	2	3	4
Other:	1	2	3	4
Other:	1	2	3	4
Other:	1	2	3	4

*B7. Are there **any other issues that we should pay attention** to while developing Network of Network to improve Science-Policy-Society interactions? Or do you have any other comments to the project team*

Thank you very much for your help.

9.2 Short questionnaire

EKLIPSE questionnaire for network representatives

Welcome to the questionnaire exploring possibilities to improve decision making regarding biodiversity and ecosystem services!

EKLIPSE invites you to describe your views on how to improve the science-policy interface related to biodiversity and ecosystem services and potential ways in which you, or your background organization, would like to contribute to the EKLIPSE mechanism.

EKLIPSE is an EU-funded project that aims to develop a mechanism for supporting better informed decisions about our environment based on the best available knowledge. This short (4 minute) [video](#) explains the EKLIPSE process and you can find out more about our science-policy activities here: <http://www.eclipse-mechanism.eu/home>

Please complete our questionnaire here. It takes approximately 15 minutes. All data will be securely stored, and anonymized. The data from the questionnaires will not be shared outside of the EKLIPSE consortium. EKLIPSE will use the results of the questionnaires in scientific research, in developing science-policy communication and to feedback to networks.

Many thanks for your collaboration!

*Q1. In your opinion, how important is it to **involve** the following actors **in science-policy-society interactions** regarding biodiversity and ecosystem services at European scale? Please rate the specific actors listed below from 1 to 5 where 1 means not at all important to involve and 5 means extremely important to involve.*

Actors to be involved	Not at all important-----Very important				
	1	2	3	4	5
Natural scientists	1	2	3	4	5
Social scientists	1	2	3	4	5
Other scientists	1	2	3	4	5
Representatives for civil society	1	2	3	4	5
Citizens	1	2	3	4	5
Decision-makers at European scale	1	2	3	4	5
Decision-makers at national scale	1	2	3	4	5
Representatives of specific networks (please use the rows below to list specific networks you think necessary to involve, if any):					
-	1	2	3	4	5
-	1	2	3	4	5
-	1	2	3	4	5

Q2. In your opinion, what **challenges** are faced when working **at the science-policy-society interface**? Please consider the following list of possible challenges and rate them on a 1-5 scale, where 1 means that the given aspect is not challenging at all, and 5 means the given aspect is highly challenging.

Challenges	Please rate the following options: 1 means not challenging at all, 5 means very challenging				
Scientific quality of the work of participating institutions or individuals.	1	2	3	4	5
Transparency concerning the information flow within the science-policy-society interface.	1	2	3	4	5
Time that members devote to the work related to the science-policy-society interface.	1	2	3	4	5
Ethical infrastructure (e.g. ombudsperson, conflict of interest policy etc.) within the science-policy-society interface.	1	2	3	4	5
Strength of relationships between the different actors of the science-policy-society interface	1	2	3	4	5
Other challenges, if any, please specify					
Other challenges, if any, please specify					
Other challenges, if any, please specify					

Q3. How **essential** do you think a process like **EKLIPSE** could be in terms of strengthening the different aspects of the science-policy-society interface?

The role of EKLIPSE in strengthening the interaction...	Not at all essential-----Very essential				
... between policy-makers and scientist	1	2	3	4	5
... between policy-makers and networks	1	2	3	4	5
... between policy-makers and civil society	1	2	3	4	5
... between networks and scientists	1	2	3	4	5
... between networks and civil society	1	2	3	4	5
... between civil society and scientists	1	2	3	4	5
The science-policy-society interface in general	1	2	3	4	5

Q4. What **role would you be interested to take in the EKLIPSE project and future science-policy mechanism**? Please consider the following options to engage with EKLIPSE and rate your interest from 1 to 3, where 1 refers to having no interest in certain roles, 2 refers to having potential interest but

lacking knowledge and/or capacity to contribute, and 3 refers to actual interest and capability to fulfilling certain roles based on your existing knowledge and capacity.

Functions within EKLIPSE	1: no interest	2: possible interest but lack of knowledge/capacity	3: actual interest based on existing knowledge/capacity
Provision of thematic expertise	1	2	3
Provision of methodological expertise	1	2	3
Knowledge hub	1	2	3
Management support	1	2	3
Provision of data/information	1	2	3
Provision of tools and infrastructure	1	2	3
Capacity building	1	2	3
Communication	1	2	3
Society and policy interaction	1	2	3
Think tank role	1	2	3
Foresight role	1	2	3
Evaluation of the work of the mechanism	1	2	3
Other role, please specify:			
Other role, please specify:			
Other role, please specify:			

Q5. What are your **expectations towards EKLIPSE**, i.e. how you could best benefit from the functions and activities of EKLIPSE?

Q6. Is there any **capacity or knowledge gaps** you would like to fill in order to work more efficiently at the science-policy-society interface? Please list no more than 5 knowledge or capacity gaps.

Q7. In your opinion, which are the **most effective ways to fulfill capacity gaps** on science-policy-society interfacing (e.g. webinars, trainings, conferences, matchmaking events)? Please list no more than 5 possible ways of capacity building.

Q8. Which of the following **communication** tools are you using to stay informed and get in touch with different actors engaged in the science-policy-society interface? Please first indicate which type of actor you represent, then choose those tools from the list below which you prefer.

Which type of actors you represent:

- science
- policy making
- civil society/citizens

Tools (please tick the tools you prefer)		Not effective-----Very effective				
		1	2	3	4	5
<input type="checkbox"/>	Personalized e-mails					
<input type="checkbox"/>	General e-mails					
<input type="checkbox"/>	Newsletters or blog					
<input type="checkbox"/>	News on the network's own website					
<input type="checkbox"/>	RSS feeds					
<input type="checkbox"/>	Twitter					
<input type="checkbox"/>	Researchgate profile of your network					
<input type="checkbox"/>	LinkedIN profile of your network					
<input type="checkbox"/>	Facebook group of your network					
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other:					
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other:					
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other:					

*Q9. Are there **any other issues that we should pay attention** to while developing the Network of Networks to improve Science-Policy-Society interactions?*

Please provide some basic contact details. This allows us to contact you and the network(s) you are affiliated with updates on project related news, calls for expertise and capacity building opportunities etc., disseminated by EKLIPSE.

- Name of the network(s) you represent/be a member:
- Your name (optional – if you wish to receive further news from EKLIPSE)
- Your e-mail address (optional – if you wish to receive further news from EKLIPSE)

Thank you very much for your help.

9.3 Interview guideline

Interview with network representatives

The EKLIPSE project is asking for your help in giving an interview about the structure and functioning of networks related to biodiversity and ecosystem services.

EKLIPSE is an EU-funded project that started in February 2016 (for more information, please visit our website: <http://www.eklipse-mechanism.eu/>). The project has five main objectives:

- To set up a light and transparent governance model for a self-sustainable support mechanism – the Network of Networks (NoN) – for evidence-based policy on biodiversity and ecosystem services in the EU;
- To coordinate innovative and transparent approaches for science, policy and societal actors to jointly provide evidence leading to better informed decision-making;
- To promote the effective engagement of all society, research and policy actors in multidisciplinary and transdisciplinary consultations to jointly identify research priorities and emerging issues related to biodiversity and ecosystem services;
- To encourage societal debate on and engagement with relevant policy and research on biodiversity and ecosystem services;
- To engage better with those networks whose knowledge has a key potential impact on biodiversity and ecosystem services.

This last objective is key to improving the science-policy-society interface. The major aim of the interview is to improve the functioning of the Network of Networks (NoN) through learning about how relevant networks work and what capacities they need to be more effective on the science-policy-society interface. With Networks we refer to different kinds of “organized exchange” – e.g. informal thematic networks, formal networks of institutions, learned societies, NGOs etc. – so please understand this term quite broadly when answering the questions.

To reach this aim, the interview focusses on two key aspects:

- How do the network you represent work and which challenges does it face?
- What can EKLIPSE do for your network? What do you see as your potential contribution to the Network of Networks?

All data will be securely stored and anonymized, and will not be shared outside of the EKLIPSE consortium. EKLIPSE will use the results of the interviews in scientific research, in developing science-policy communication and to give feedback to networks.

We are grateful for your collaboration!

Q1. What are the major **objectives/functions** of your network?

Q2. Who are your **partners/participants**? Please choose the types of membership most typical for your network from the list below (you can choose more than one option).

10. Individual researchers
11. Individual practitioners (e.g. landscape managers, engineers)
12. Business actors (e.g. entrepreneurs, companies, representatives of business interest groups)
13. Research or educational bodies (e.g. research institutes, universities)
14. Representatives of non-governmental organizations
15. Representatives of governmental organizations (e.g. legislator or administrative bodies)
16. Other, please specify:
17. Other, please specify:
18. Other, please specify:

Q3. How is your network **governed**? Please describe briefly the governance structure of your network in terms of the main governance entities that lead/support your network.

Q3.1. Which one of the synthetic governance structures, listed below, describes the best the functioning of your network?

5. Network governed by its participants (no separate and/or unique governance entity exists)
6. Network governed by a lead organization (major activities and key decisions rest with the central organization which taken the leading role)
7. Network governed by an administrative organization, established by partners of the network
8. Other

Q4. How are **decisions made** in your network? Please describe briefly the key decision making mechanisms – including formal institutions (e.g. general assembly meetings), as well as informal mechanisms, if any (e.g. the role of personal knowledge exchange) – in terms of their scope, frequency, and the links between them.

Q4.1. Which one of the synthetic decision making models, listed below, describes the best the decision making processes within your network?

6. Decisions are solely made by the governing body in a centralized way.
7. Decision making follows a consultative model where the governing body/organization makes the decision, based on feedback received from within the membership.
8. Decisions are prepared (e.g. alternatives identified and compared) by the governing body/organization, while the final decisions are by the general assembly or equivalent institution.
9. Decisions are proposed/prepared on a voluntary basis by the membership, decisions are made by the general assembly or equivalent institution.
10. Other

Q5. What is the **funding model** of your network? Please choose the types of funding sources most typical for your network from the list below (you can choose more than one option).

7. Payments/fees from individual members
8. Payments from member organizations
9. One main funding source, please specify (e.g. DG, governmental body etc.):
10. Contracts/ projects
11. Fundraising, please specify:
12. Other

Q5.1. If possible please provide some more explanation on the funding model of your network and challenges you face regarding funding.

*Q6. What **key strengths** do you think your network has?*

*Q7. What **challenges** is your network facing recently? If possible, please also provide a brief explanation of why the listed issues are challenging in particular.*

*Q8. What are your **expectations towards EKLIPSE**, i.e. how your network could best benefit from the functions and activities of EKLIPSE? Please note that by EKLIPSE **mechanism** we refer to the science-policy-society interface being developed in the EKLIPSE project to support evidence-informed decision-making affecting biodiversity and ecosystem services.*

*Q9. In your opinion, how could your network **contribute to** an organized science-policy-society interface process, like EKLIPSE (e.g. in terms of expertise, management support, foresight etc.)?*

Possible contributions to science-policy-society interface processes	Level of interest			Comments, explanation
	1: no interest;	2: possible interest but lack of knowledge/ capacity;	3: actual interest based on existing knowledge / capacity	
Provision of thematic expertise	1	2	3	
Provision of methodological expertise	1	2	3	
Knowledge hub	1	2	3	
Management support	1	2	3	
Provision of data/information	1	2	3	
Provision of tools and infrastructure	1	2	3	
Capacity building	1	2	3	
Communication	1	2	3	
Society and policy interactions	1	2	3	
Think tank role	1	2	3	
Foresight role	1	2	3	
Evaluation of the process(es)	1	2	3	
Other role, please specify:				
Other role, please specify:				
Other role, please specify:				

Q10. Which **capacities should be improved** in your network to be able to fully mobilize your assets?

Q11. Which are the **most effective ways to fulfill capacity gaps** in your network (e.g. webinars, trainings, conferences, matchmaking events)? Please also provide us brief example(s) of best practices for capacity building, if any.

Q12. Which are the **most efficient ways of communication** in your network (e.g. generalized or personal e-mails, newsletters, website, twitter or other social media etc.). If possible, please make a distinction between those communication tools which are better to inform members (i.e. one-way communication) and those which are better to trigger feedback (i.e. two-way communication).

Q13. Below we list some networks/hubs that were reported in the KNEU project as having significant impact on science-policy interaction concerning biodiversity and ecosystem services in Europe. Please consider if your network has any **direct or indirect links** with the listed ones. Please feel free to add other networks that you think significant in this field.

Name of organization/network/project	I have not yet heard about it.	I have heard about it but not been involved.	My network have minor collaboration with it.	My network has strong collaboration with it.
COPA-COGECA	1	2	3	4
EEA (European Environmental Agency)	1	2	3	4
EEB (European Environmental Bureau)	1	2	3	4
EPBRS (European Platform for Biodiversity Research Strategy)	1	2	3	4
European Commission: DG Agri	1	2	3	4
European Commission: DG Environment	1	2	3	4
European Commission: DG Mare	1	2	3	4
European Commission: DG Research	1	2	3	4
EU funded research projects on ecosystem services and biodiversity (e.g. BESAFE, ESMERALDA, LIBERATION, OpenNESS, OPERAs, QuESSA etc.)	1	2	3	4
EuroMarine (European Marine Research Network)	1	2	3	4
Future Earth / DIVERSITAS	1	2	3	4
GBIF (Global Biodiversity Information Facility)	1	2	3	4
Global and regional scientific assessments, such as IPCC, IPBES, TEEB, MA, CoML	1	2	3	4

ICES (International Council for the Exploration of the Sea)	1	2	3	4
International Conventions (e.g. the Bern Convention, CBD, Ramsar etc.)	1	2	3	4
International and European NGOs such as WWF, Birdlife, Greenpeace etc.	1	2	3	4
IUCN	1	2	3	4
JRC (Joint Research Centre of the European Commission)	1	2	3	4
UN and its organizations (e.g. UNEP, FAO, UNESCO, UNDP)	1	2	3	4
Other:	1	2	3	4
Other:	1	2	3	4
Other:	1	2	3	4
Other:	1	2	3	4
Other:	1	2	3	4

Q14. Are there **any other issues that we should pay attention** to while developing Network of Network to improve Science-Policy-Society interactions?

Thank you very much for your help.

9.4 List of networks contacted for the interview

Acronym	Full name	Type of interview	Level	Type of network
ALTER-Net	A Long-Term Biodiversity, Ecosystem and Awareness Research Network	Interview (second phase)	EU	Science-policy interface
AtlantOS	Optimising and Enhancing the Integrated Atlantic Ocean Observing Systems	Interview (second phase)	International	Research project
BiodivERsA	BiodivERsA	Interview (second phase)	EU	Science-policy interface
CEEWEB	Central and Eastern European Web for Biodiversity	Interview (second phase)	Regional (sub-European)	NGO
ECOPOTENTIAL	ECOPOTENTIAL: improving future ecosystem benefits through earth observations	Interview (second phase)	EU	Research project
ECSA	European Citizen Science Association	No answer	(Pan-)European	NGO
ECSITE	European Collaborative for Science, Industry and Technology Exhibitions	No answer	Global	Expert/Practitioner network
EEB	European Environment Bureau	Interview (second phase)	(Pan-) European	NGO
EFB	European Federation of Green Roof Associations	Interview (second phase)	(Pan-)European	Expert/Practitioner network
EHF	European Habitats Forum	No answer	EU	Expert/Practitioner network
EPBRS	European Platform for Biodiversity Research Strategy	Interview (second phase)	EU	Science-policy interface
ESA-ES	European Sociological Association, Environment and Society Network	Long questionnaire (first phase)	(Pan-)European	Learned society
ESEE	European Society for Ecological Economics	Interview (second phase)	EU	Learned society
ESMERALDA	Enhancing ecoSystem sERVICES mApping for poLicy and Decision mAKing	Interview (second phase)	(Pan-)European	Research project
ESRS	European Society for Rural Sociology	Interview (second phase)	(Pan-)European	Learned society
EuroMarine	European Marine Research Network	Interview (second phase)	EU	Science-policy interface
EUROPARC	EUROPARC Federation	No answer	(Pan-)European	Expert/Practitioner network
EUROSITE	Eurosite	Interview (second phase)	(Pan-)European	Expert/Practitioner network
EW	Earthwatch	Interview (second phase)	Global, (Pan) European, EU	NGO
GENIALG	GENetic diversity exploitation for Innovative Macro-ALGal biorefinery	Interview (second phase)	(Pan-)European	Research project
Geobon	Group on Earth Observations Biodiversity Observation Network	Interview (first phase)	Global	Science-policy interface

GMC	Greifswald Mire Centre	Long questionnaire (first phase)	Global, (Pan) European, National	Expert/Practitioner network
HERCULES	Sustainable Futures for Europe's Heritage in Cultural Landscapes	Interview (second phase)	EU	Research project
IALE-Europe	International Association for Landscape Ecology, European chapter	No answer	(Pan-)European	Learned society
ICES	International Council for the Exploration of the Seas	Interview (second phase)	International	Science-policy interface
ICLEI Europe	ICLEI - Local Governments for Sustainability	No answer	Global, (Pan) European, EU	Expert/Practitioner network
IUCN	IUCN Europe	Interview (second phase)	Global	NGO
Leverage Points	Leverage Points for Sustainability Transformation	Long questionnaire (first phase)	National, Sub-national	Project
MERCES	Marine Ecosystem Restoration in Changing European Seas	Interview (second phase)	(Pan-)European	Research project
NeFo	Network-Forum Biodiversity Research Germany	Long questionnaire (first phase)	National	Science-policy interface
OPPLA	OPPLA	Interview (second phase)	Global, (Pan) European, EU	Science-policy interface
PPK	Platform for Research of Landscape and Ecosystem Services (Platforma pro Krajinu)	Long questionnaire (first phase)	National	Science-policy interface
SCB-ES	Society for Conservation Biology - Europe Section	Interview (second phase)	Global, (Pan) European, EU	Learned society
SER Europe	Society for Ecological Restoration	No answer	(Pan-)European	Learned society